

Modern media space in the world international competition and information in the case of area s

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Abstract. This article analyzes the opinions about the theoretical-pedagogical, scientific foundations of the international competition of the media space and the information space in the modern world based on primary sources.

The demand for print media in modern society is determined by how successfully they act as a means of mass communication in society, they provide such information that helps individuals, groups and other social entities to actively participate in cognitive, educational, axiological, organizational activities. forms relationships. X behavior and other social processes. Such communication is impossible without a complete, vivid and objective image of the current reality presented to the mass audience by the press. It is impossible without adequately reflecting the spiritual potential of society, which is manifested in the real conditions of the life of various social groups, without creating a collection of publications whose content reflects the current reality in all its diversity and completeness. the basis of the real events taking place in it.

Without full journalistic education, it is difficult for a person to form an adequate reaction to the happenings, to determine the priority directions of the flow, to understand the positive and negative, to oppose manipulative messages, assumptions and fabrications, and to actively participate. in the processes of expression and formation of public opinion. The need to popularize politics, economics, science, spiritual, spiritual, practical and other types of practical activities determines the great responsibility of print media in the implementation of communicative functions aimed at ensuring mutual cooperation of various social groups of society. . first of all, those formed in the system of social division of labor. In fact, it is the responsibility of a person, group, organization for the behavior of various social entities that should be formed in society in accordance with the real life conditions.

Today, the global changes taking place in the environment surrounding print media have a significant impact on their character. This is primarily related to changes in the economic, political, and technological layers of society. It is

necessary to take into account the modern print media, which is related to the development of journalism, defining transparency as an integral result of the interaction of the mass media system with all spheres of public life. Revealing them requires an in-depth analysis of the processes related to press activities during the years of independence. Among them is the transformation of mass information space. Each evolutionary process in nature and society, as an important part of human history, brings mankind closer to clarifying the historical truth about itself. In this sense, he explores the important innovation of the creation of the world from the history of the creation of the earth, the interrelationship of the animal kingdom and the flora.[3.25]

Due to the deep penetration of media literacy and information culture into our lives, the amount of information has also increased, and in such a global process, journalism is the best guarantee of public democratic dialogue. This type of communication is a key factor in the realization of human rights.

The new social division of labor created new subjects of information relations, reorganized and expanded the composition of communicative functions of various social subjects, involved mass media in their implementation. This applies primarily to the communicative functions of purely economic activity. But intersubjective relations in the political sphere, in the sphere of culture and science have also changed significantly. The Internet has added new technological possibilities to this interaction. As a result, segmentation occurred in the information space reinforced by the needs of the developing market: its participants needed a target audience to sell their goods and services to increase the efficiency of production and commercial activities. All this together predetermined the shifts in the mass information system: the changes affected their typological structure. Adaptation of media types to the specific conditions of communication in a competitive environment has begun. With the help of partial modification of typological characteristics, the possibility of achieving great commercial success was created. This process can be defined as formatting the media type.

The countries that gained independence in the 90s of the 20th century had to adapt to the demands of globalization processes, which are increasingly reaching their climax, while creating a path of independent development. There are so many definitions of the phenomenon of globalization that no matter how different they are, they all have one big truth - that globalization is generalization, integration, interconnectedness and cooperation in one form or another. is emphasized, repeated. Another fact is that globalization , in a broad sense, is more and more reflected in the globalization of information . This situation has changed the concept of information and mass media in general in the world media space. The emerging

"new world information order" has put new tasks before any country. In addition, adaptation to this situation began to gain decisive importance in the formation of the international image of an independent state.[6.89]

So what is international journalism? How is the world media space understood? What are their directions, interests, and laws? What are the demands and tasks of the journalists of our country due to the influence of global news confrontations and ideological and political technologies? What new demands does Uzbekistan's integration into the world of international journalism make for our journalists? The ability to find answers to such questions from both theoretical and practical points of view remains a criterion that indicates the modernity of the society and the state, its progress at the level of the requirements of the time, and ultimately, how perfectly the image of the people and the state is being created.

In the current era of globalization of information, the activities of the press and mass media in the countries of the world as a system are becoming an unimaginable, incredible flow. This stream, which is one of the incredible inventions of human intelligence and civilization, is called "world journalism", "international journalism".

Humanity has reached a new stage of development in which new cooperative relations called "globalization" have been established, and these relations are rapidly expanding and deepening. As a result, the word "globalization" has become a concept that encompasses not only economic, but also social-political, spiritual-educational, and almost all other spheres of universal human processes.

Globalization of information has created commonalities and similarities in the conditions of the countries of the world and in our socio-political, spiritual and educational life. As a result of this: firstly, the recognition that the only reasonable way to build a high-level advanced society in the world is to build a democratic-legal state; secondly, it became impossible to deny that one of the main signs and conditions of a democratic-legal society is the freedom of mass media; thirdly, the possibilities of spreading the best practices achieved in the field of press liberalization of a developed country to far and near countries have increased; fourthly, many important international documents capable of covering international schools of journalism were created and implemented; fifthly, the habit of observing the state of press freedom in the countries of the world on an international scale, commenting on them, giving an assessment and forming the opinion of the world public about the situation in a particular country on this basis has become somewhat popular.

The listed cases, of course, are turning the world into a unified information space.

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It must be admitted that now the power and potential of states is measured by how much information they have. Most importantly, competition for information ownership is more intense than ever. This process itself accelerates the decision-making and development of international journalism, and ultimately the generalization of features of global journalism. According to Doctor of Philological Sciences H. Dostmuhamedov, this situation puts on the agenda the need to study and analyze national journalism from the point of view of world journalism, and at the same time world journalism from the point of view of national journalism.

In our opinion, the world media space, the special place and importance of international journalism, as well as the role of national journalism in the world media space, are among the relevant issues.

has its own values, meanings and directions. In general, represents a concept.

International journalism is inextricably linked with diplomacy, and it pays special attention to the necessity of wide use of social, legal and political norms of mutual cooperation between nations. Also, national-cultural peculiarities, values, mentality and moral-educational norms, traditions and beliefs are also structural elements of international journalism.

In fact, the issues of democracy and human rights, war and peace, drugs, terrorism, environmental problems, as well as the integration of European countries into the world community can be seen and observed on almost all major media pages in the world.

When talking about the general similarities characteristic of national journalism schools in the countries of the world, at the same time, it should not be overlooked that there are certain differences in the journalism of each country. It should be noted that former socialist countries form the main group of countries where the field of journalism is rapidly changing and mass media are experiencing complex processes. After all, socio-political and economic changes in the society determine the direction of activity of periodical press, radio and television. For this reason, development trends in young independent countries are causing fundamental changes in national journalism.

In fact, regardless of whether they belong to the "West" and have similar cultural origins, the journalism of European and American countries differs from each other in many aspects. In general, in the journalism of the European continent, giving an "opinion" representing the author's point of view (i.e., "Journalism of Opinions") occupies a dominant position, while in American and British journalism, it relies more on concrete evidence and facts, in other words, the press the news distributed by the representatives of the society as socially significant news began to

be appreciated more and more. The speed and intensity of life and lifestyle in the US and UK has made it imperative to get facts and evidence as quickly as possible. As a result, a unique "inverted ihram" method of writing news material was created, and this custom formed the tradition of keeping the names of reporters anonymous in most newspapers.

Journalism of Uzbekistan, as is known, appeared and developed under the influence of Russian journalism. At the same time, the development model of the journalism of the European continent is not alien to us.

In the 20th century, international journalism mainly serves as a kind of weapon between the "two poles". The ideological, biased, intensely political character of journalism remained until the 90s of the twentieth century. The collapse of the USSR and the end of the "Cold War" relations completely changed the nature of international journalism.

But we cannot ignore another problem. "Leading politicians of underdeveloped countries," writes Mia Dornert, chairwoman of "UNESCO's Press Freedom Advisory Group," often complain about the imbalance in the international information flow, with rich Western countries leading the way. In their opinion, participation in the free flow of information without equality cannot be compromised. Based on this, they are demanding that UNESCO should deal with the issue of closing the gap between "wealthy" and "poor" countries in terms of information.

In 1978, for the first time, the concept of "New World Information Order" was legally recognized at the international level. The document was officially adopted by the UN General Assembly and the UNESCO General Conference. UNESCO's Declaration of Basic Principles on the Contribution of Mass Communication to the Promotion of Peace and Understanding among Peoples specifically states: should not. At this point, it is necessary to provide wide access to messages from Uzbekistan." In 1980, a separate resolution was adopted by UNESCO on the control (or licensing) of the flow of news and various cultural products in the international arena. In the same year, a new organization named "International Program for the Development of Communications" began to operate on the initiative of UNESCO.

A number of developed countries did not like such innovations implemented by an influential international organization. According to the representatives of these countries, it seems that the system implemented by UNESCO is a control of activities in this regard, contrary to the democratic traditions of the Western press, and in general, it destroys the free dissemination of information in the world.

It's no secret that at the same time, using the Internet only for their own interests is becoming one of the main goals of Western countries. In developed countries,

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serious attention is being paid to the issue of strengthening cyber security, as well as the use of the Internet for the purpose of military-psychological influence. Some countries prefer to subordinate the Internet directly to their goals, while others are developing a measure of protection by limiting it.

There are many examples of this. For example, in the Islamic Republic of Iran, work is underway to cut off the country from the external Internet and create a completely national internal "spider web". China is taking technical measures to completely close foreign social networks and filter text.

In 2012, the US administration announced the first international strategy for Kibe ramakon in the world. Based on this document, it is envisaged to create a favorable media environment in the country through the effective use of cyber technologies. It should be noted that experts evaluate this as an attempt by the United States to directly influence people's minds on a global scale. In "Rossiyskaya Gazeta" "The US State Department is working to start a new war with Russia." the sensational message that " he is crying " was published. "In this war, the computer was chosen as the main weapon of invasion, and the Internet was chosen for the battlefield." According to the plan, all sites, blogs and chats operating in Russian will be put under severe pressure and pressure. According to one of the officials of the service entrusted with this task (it is called "External Digital Communications Team" - BA), such an information battle on the Internet waves is also conducted in Arabic, Persian and Urdu languages.

One of the serious problems arising in the information war is the level of development of the countries that have established cooperation relations. Let's say that a powerful state has reached an agreement on cooperation with a young independent state that has not yet developed. And a powerful state does not tire of controlling a young independent partner state in any way, while a state that does not yet have such an opportunity remains passive. So, can cooperative equality be maintained in this case? "The extremely powerful ICT capability created in the USA causes such concern," writes Professor A. Krutskikh, a special employee of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation. - If one of the partner parties has the opportunity to control the goals of the other party, and the other party is deprived of this opportunity, can we call such cooperation equal?"

In short, US international strategy in cyberspace is becoming increasingly sophisticated. Under this pretext, the commitment of the US to create "reliable, safe and secure platforms" to ensure freedom of speech and association is questioned by many, especially experts of countries that oppose US hegemony.

Countries that have been opposing each other on the world stage since time immemorial - sometimes openly, sometimes covertly - are creating completely new

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battlefields from the miracle of the Internet and information. The saddest thing is that journalism and mass media, which serve for goodness, are being turned into warriors of those battlefields. Many countries have started preparations for information warfare. Countless funds are being mobilized for this purpose. It is not necessary to break the traditional borders for the information war, moreover, in this war, people are not massacred, but the worldviews of the general public are influenced by the "cooperation" of telecommunications and mass media systems.

The important thing is that no state or center will be able to limit or control such systems except powerful states. "Actually," writes Uzbek publicist J. Melikulov, "behind this lies the desire to introduce ideas adapted to Western values and patterns to the whole world and thereby expand its sphere of influence." The goal is to export consciousness." World media space - the place and importance of international journalism in the fate of humanity, including states, peoples, and nations at the current historical stage, is so great that, in a word, "It is worth noting that today, when the whole world has become a single information space day by day, the struggle between good teachings and evil ideas that call people to perfection is getting more and more intense.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the analysis of world journalism, it is certainly not possible to fully cover all the processes and new trends taking place in it. But at the same time, it is necessary for our national journalism to examine the national identities that are still preserved without harming the national interests, and to determine the somewhat effective principles that will be used in the process of striving towards the information society.

Globalization and the rapid pace of current life, scientific and technical progress, new information technologies are rapidly changing our life and society in general. In such a situation, the demands of the human society towards journalists are also changing. In fact, in today's advanced age, radical changes have been made in the field of mass media, like all other fields. It is necessary to train professional fighters - journalists, in order to withstand informational attacks, which are more powerful than nuclear test sites, and the "date tricks" of the new civilization - the process of globalization. In the global news space, it is permissible for journalists to act as politicians, statesmen, and defenders of the nation.

As it is repeatedly emphasized in the press, interviews, researches and analyzes published by experts, "Today, through information technology, the practice of deliberately distorting the true situation in another country, purposefully influencing the mood of the political leadership and citizens there is becoming more and more widespread. This remains a big problem for the world community."

Based on the opinions and analyzes presented in this article, the following conclusions were drawn: - the processes of globalization, along with many changes, created a completely new world information order, which is almost identical in large and small countries . demanded the radical reform of all spheres , including the information and mass media; - in the conditions of the new world information order, features common to all countries of the world were formed, in this case, the establishment of international relations, mutual experience made sharing easier;

- two different trends were observed in world journalism: the first - almost all countries experienced similar reform processes, and the second - at the same time, each country followed its own and appropriate path. In particular, the young independent states tried to balance and ensure harmony between these two paths. This situation also gained special importance in increasing and strengthening the international image of the states;

- in the conditions of globalization, attempts to occupy the world's information space, tendencies to aspire to its absolute ownership are clearly visible. This paves the way for the monopolization of information in the international media space, and in some cases, it is reflected in the actions of powerful countries that do not take into account the interests of young countries that are just developing and have just chosen the path of independence; - the real conditions in the world media space and the constant changes require special attention to be paid to the issue of professionalization in a broad sense in our milky journalism.

LIST OF REFERENCES.

1. SH.M. Mirziyoyev " We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level " - Tashkent , "Uzbekistan " , 2017, page 592, page 10.
- 2 . Incheon d e c l a r a t i o n // E d u c a t i o n 2 0 3 0 : G o o d s d s i n c l u s i v e o a t h e q u i t a b l e q u a l i t y e d u c a t i o n a n d n d l i f e l o n g l e a r n i n g f o r a l l (W o r d E d u c a t i o n F o r u m , 1 9 - 2 2 M a y 2 0 1 5 . I n c h e o n , R e p u b l i c o f K o r e a) . - 4 8 p . 3 .
3. Muslimov NA "Professional formation of future vocational education teachers" / Monograph.-Tashkent.: Science, 2004, 360 pages.
4. Saidahmedov N. "Pedagogical skill and pedagogical technology". - Tashkent: "Science and technology" - 2003, 340 pages.
5. RAMavlonova, NHRakhmonkulova, KOMatnazarova, MKShirinov, S. Hafizov "General pedagogy" - Tashkent, "Fan va tekhnologiya" publishing house, 2018, 530 pages.
6. Safarov, BN (2022). PEARLS-ADVANCE IN THE STUDY OF INTERNATIONAL READING LITERACY. Innovative development in educational activities, 1 (5), 134-138.

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7. Safarov, BN (2022, November). EFFECTIVENESS OF ORGANIZING PEDAGOGICAL COACHING IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS. AT THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY (Volume 1, Issue 8, Pages 30-35).
8. Safarov, B. (2021). Importance of mathematics lessons in preparing 6-7 year old children for school education: Importance of mathematics lessons in preparing 6-7 year old children for school education. *Journal of Early Childhood Education*, 2 (2).
9. Norboyevich, SB, & Akhmadjonovna, BM (2023). MANAGEMENT PRINCIPLES OF EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. *Innovative development in educational activities*, 2 (4), 18-23.
10. Tayirov M. REQUIREMENTS FOR PROFESSIONAL CULTURE OF FUTURE TEACHERS // *Journal Pedagogical i psychology c sovremennom education – 2021. – no. 3.*
11. Meliev X. A. , Safarov B. N. O ILA , SCHOOL AND SCHOOL EDUCATION ORGANIZATION COOPERATION IMPROVE CONTENT // *Academic research in educational sciences. - 2021. - T. 2. – no. 11. - S. 1312-1316.*
12. Boltakov S., Begaliyeva H. THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATIVE THINKING IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS // *Akademicheskije Isledovaniya c sovremennoy science - 2023. - T. 2. – no. 9. - S. 129-132.*
13. Norboyevich, Safarov Botir. "IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL-METHODICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAMS (PIRLS)." *KOKAN UNIVERSITY BULLETIN 1* (2023): 103-105.
14. Norboyevich, Safarov Botir, and Nabiyeva Gulnora. "IMPORTANCE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN MENTAL EDUCATION OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS." *CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND APPLIED SCIENCES IN SCIENTIFIC INNOVATIVE RESEARCH* . Vol. 1. No. 1. 2024.
- 15 . www.jdpu.uz
16. www.tdpu.uz
- 17 . www.arxiv.uz